

Original Article

Comparative Evaluation of Osseointegration of Ti, Ti-Ga and Ga-Si-Ti Alloy Implant Using Digital Direct Radiography *In Vivo*

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This study aimed to evaluate bone mineral density (BMD) and osseointegration using digital radiography following the implantation of newly synthesized metallic biomaterials into rat femur. Implants composed of Titanium (Ti), Titanium-Gallium (Ti-Ga), and Gallium-Silicon-Titanium (Ga-Si-Ti) alloys were assessed over a period of 56 days. Radiographic imaging was performed using two modalities: Posterior-Anterior (PA) whole-body digital radiography and intraoral paralleling radiography. PA images were used for qualitative assessment, while quantitative bone density measurements were obtained using calibrated grayscale analysis and digital subtraction techniques. Linear BMD was measured at multiple time points (days 14, 28, 42, and 56) in cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone regions. Statistical analysis revealed that the Ga-Si-Ti group exhibited the highest bone mineral density in newly formed bone, followed by Ti-Ga and Ti groups. Notably, newly formed bone around Ga-Si-Ti implants achieved mineralization earlier (day 28), as compared to Ti-Ga (day 42) and Ti (day 56). The application of quantitative 2D digital radiography enabled early detection of osseointegration and demonstrated its effectiveness as a non-invasive, reproducible method for *in vivo* bone regeneration studies.

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Introduction

Commercially pure Titanium (Cp-Ti) has been extensively utilized as a core biomaterial in dental implant manufacturing due to its high biocompatibility and corrosion resistance. However, the inherent softness of Cp-Ti limits its mechanical strength, particularly under load-bearing conditions. To overcome this drawback, titanium is often alloyed with other elements such as aluminum and vanadium. Alloys like Ti-6Al-4V, Ti-6Al-7Nb, and Ti-13Nb-13Z are commonly used, but they present certain biological concerns aluminum has been linked to metabolic bone diseases such as osteomalacia and Alzheimer's disease, while vanadium exhibits cytotoxicity to living cells [1].

To address these limitations, research has turned to the development of novel titanium alloys that exhibit enhanced strength, biocompatibility, and osseointegration. Silicon (Si) is

recognized as an essential trace element for bone formation [2], and its incorporation into Titanium alloys has been shown to improve both mechanical and biological properties [3]. Gallium (Ga), on the other hand, has been reported to have antiresorptive effects by inhibiting osteoclast-mediated bone resorption without cytotoxicity [4]. Additionally, Ga is metallurgically analogous to aluminum, allowing easy incorporation into titanium matrices [5,6].

Previous studies have demonstrated that Ga-Si-Ti alloys exhibit favorable mechanical properties and biological responses. For example, Antonova et al. [3] reported optimal strength and ductility in Ti-5(Si-Ga3), and Sivakumar et al. [7] confirmed the alloy's potential in dental applications. Since Si promotes bone formation and Ga inhibits bone resorption, their combined effect is hypothesized to enhance osseointegration. Liu et al. [8] recommended further *in vivo* animal studies to validate this synergistic potential prior to clinical trials.

Digital radiography has emerged as a valuable tool in preclinical research for assessing implant integration and bone remodeling.

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It provides numerous advantages, including real-time visualization, image enhancement, reproducibility, and non-destructive longitudinal monitoring. Subtraction radiography, in particular, enhances the detection of subtle bone changes by eliminating anatomical background noise through standardized image acquisition protocols. Prior investigations using PA views of digital radiographs in rodent models [9, 10] have primarily focused on qualitative assessments of implant positioning and peri-implant bone response.

While these approaches have provided foundational insights, they remain largely subjective. Therefore, this study introduces a novel methodology based on quantitative analysis using two-dimensional (2D) digital radiography. By applying grayscale-calibrated image analysis and subtraction techniques, the present work offers a reproducible and objective assessment of bone mineral density (BMD) around dental implants. This approach aligns with current trends in biomaterials research that emphasize standardized, image-based evaluation methods for osseointegration performance. To evaluate the osseointegration property of the newly synthesized Ga-Si-Ti implant in comparison with Ti and Ti-Ga implants.

Materials and Methods

Ethical approval

The study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA) and the National Institutes of Health (NIH) for the care and use of laboratory animals. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee of Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology (IAEC Number: SU/CLATR/IAEC/XV/152/2020).

Surgical procedures

Eight-week-old Wistar rats (200–250 g) were used for the in vivo implantation study. General anesthesia was administered via the intraperitoneal route using ketamine (40–90 mg/kg) and xylazine (5–10 mg/kg). A stab incision was made along the lateral aspect of the femur to expose the medial surface. A standardized bone defect (2 mm × 3 mm) was created using a 1.5 mm surgical drill. The experimental implants - commercially pure titanium (Ti), titanium-gallium (Ti-Ga), and gallium-silicon-titanium (Ga-Si-Ti) - were

placed into the defect sites. Wound closure was performed using 3-0 silk sutures, and Healex spray was applied topically. Postoperative care included administration of gentamycin (antibiotic), buprenorphine (analgesic), and maintenance of hydration using dextrose saline.

Radiographic techniques

Posterior-anterior (PA) radiography

Digital radiographs were acquired on days 14, 28, 42, and 56 post-implantation using a Sirona Orthophos Xg radiographic machine. Standard and follow-up images were aligned, and digital subtraction was performed to evaluate bone density changes. Sidexis Xg software was used for grayscale analysis to quantify mineralization and newly formed bone. Qualitative assessment was based on grayscale variations indicating mineral loss (hypodensity) or gain (hyperdensity).

Paralleling technique radiography

High-resolution digital images were obtained using the X-Mind intraoral X-ray unit (60 kVp, 4 mA, 0.4 s exposure time). Imaging was performed with phosphor storage plates processed using the Soredex Digora Optime system. Regions of interest (cortical bone, trabecular bone, and newly formed bone) were selected for grayscale analysis. Densitometric measurements were expressed as point grayscale values to assess bone mineralization around the implant sites.

Statistical analysis

For PA radiographic data, linear bone density was compared between implanted and contralateral normal bone using the Mann-Whitney U test. Intergroup comparisons (Ti, Ti-Ga, and Ga-Si-Ti) were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis test.

In digital subtraction radiography, differences in newly formed bone density on days 14 and 28 were analyzed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (within-group) and the Kruskal-Wallis test (between-group). For the paralleling technique, grayscale values representing point density were compared among groups using the Kruskal-Wallis test. These methodologies ensured a comprehensive and statistically robust assessment of bone density and osseointegration across all implant groups.

Figure 1: PA view of whole-body (a) digital radiograph and (b) subtraction image in the Ti group at day 28, showing minimal newly formed bone as indicated by grayscale variation

Figure 2: PA view of whole-body (a) digital radiograph and (b) subtraction image in the Ti-Ga group. Moderate new bone formation is observed in (b)

Figure 3: (a) PA radiograph and (b) subtraction image for Ga-Si-Ti group. Enhanced grayscale intensity in (b) indicates significant early bone formation by day 28

Results

Radiographic evaluation using posterior-anterior (PA) view

Posterior-Anterior (PA) whole-body radiographs and subtraction images were obtained for each group: Ti (figure 1a and b), Ti-Ga (figure 2a and b), and Ga-Si-Ti (figure 3a and b). Bone mineral density (BMD) measurements were taken on days 14, 28, 42, and 56 in four anatomical regions: medial cortical, lateral cortical, trabecular bone, and newly formed bone. The results for each implant group, comparing the implanted and adjacent non-implanted sides, are presented in tables 1, 2, and 3. In the Ti group (table 1), no statistically significant differences were found in cortical or trabecular bone between the two sides; however, newly formed bone showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$). The Ti-Ga group (table 2) also showed no significant differences in cortical or trabecular regions, but newly formed bone exhibited a statistically significant increase in density. The Ga-Si-Ti group (table 3) followed the same trend, with significant differences only observed in newly formed bone between the implanted and non-implanted sides.

Intergroup comparison of newly formed bone among the three implant groups is shown in table 4. Pairwise comparisons using the Mann-Whitney U test (table 5) revealed significant differences in newly formed bone between the Ti and Ti-Ga groups on days

Figure 4: Paralleling radiographs showing regions of interest: (a) cortical, (b) trabecular, and (c) newly formed bone density measurements

Table 1: Comparison of linear bone density (medial cortical, lateral cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone) between the implanted and non-implanted femur in the Ti group

Bone type	Group	14 th Day	28 th Day	42 nd Day	56 th Day
Medial cortical bone	Normal bone	42.6 ± 6.14	47.6 ± 0.89	43.8 ± 5.26	47.4 ± 1.14
	Implanted bone	44 ± 7.9	46 ± 1.58	43.4 ± 3.84	46 ± 1.58
	p-value	0.293	0.105	0.753	0.167
Lateral cortical bone	Normal bone	44.6 ± 3.97	47.6 ± 0.54	41.6 ± 6.69	44.2 ± 1.3
	Implanted bone	44.8 ± 6.05	43.6 ± 4.27	39.2 ± 4.71	44.8 ± 2.86
	p-value	0.454	0.514	0.528	0.671
Trabecular bone	Normal bone	40 ± 4.79	43.2 ± 3.42	38.4 ± 3.13	44.6 ± 1.14
	Implanted bone	41.6 ± 6.98	40 ± 2.23	36.8 ± 3.11	45.4 ± 2.07
	p-value	0.335	0.171	0.528	0.595
Newly formed bone	Normal bone	0	0	0	0
	Implanted bone	0	17±2.23	27.8±4.71	43.2±1.92
	p-value	-	0.005*	0.005*	0.005*

Table 2: Comparison of linear bone density (medial cortical, lateral cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone) between the implanted and non-implanted femur in the Ti-Ga group

Bone type	Group	14 th Day	28 th Day	42 nd Day	56 th Day
Medial cortical bone	Normal bone	53 ± 13.54	54 ± 10.12	57.2 ± 6.49	58 ± 4.63
	Implanted bone	56.8 ± 11.94	61.2 ± 8.07	63 ± 7.9	60.2 ± 7.08
	p-value	0.402	0.175	0.175	0.463
Lateral cortical bone	Normal bone	54.2 ± 13.31	51 ± 9.3	56.4 ± 8.79	53.8 ± 10.96
	Implanted bone	54.4 ± 12.34	55.6 ± 6.87	63.8 ± 1.78	56.6 ± 7.12
	p-value	0.917	0.402	0.454	0.675
Trabecular bone	Normal bone	51 ± 5.61	50.6 ± 5.22	51 ± 5.61	47 ± 4.3
	Implanted bone	45.4 ± 10.16	54.6 ± 2.6	55.4 ± 9.6	49.2 ± 7.42
	p-value	0.598	0.136	0.596	0.530
Newly formed bone	Normal bone	0	0	0	0
	Implanted bone	0	44.4 ± 2.6	54.6 ± 9.6	50.8 ± 7.42
	p-value	-	0.005*	0.005*	0.005*

Table 3: Comparison of linear bone density (medial cortical, lateral cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone) between the implanted and non-implanted femur in the Ga-Si-Ti group

Bone type	Group	14 th Day	28 th Day	42 nd Day	56 th Day
Medial cortical bone	Normal bone	41 ± 6.32	57 ± 4.84	60.2 ± 7.08	63 ± 7.9
	Implanted bone	44.6 ± 6.22	57.8 ± 5.63	58 ± 4.63	57.2 ± 6.49
	p-value	0.173	0.675	0.463	0.175
Lateral cortical bone	Normal bone	41.2 ± 2.38	55 ± 4.3	56.6 ± 7.12	63.8 ± 1.788
	Implanted bone	40.4 ± 7.19	56.8 ± 6.9	53.8 ± 10.96	56.4 ± 8.79
	p-value	1.000	0.599	0.675	0.454
Trabecular bone	Normal bone	42.6 ± 4.92	61.8 ± 6.05	49.2 ± 7.42	45.4 ± 9.6
	Implanted bone	41 ± 6.2	56 ± 3.87	53.2 ± 4.14	45.2 ± 1.92
	p-value	0.458	0.175	0.402	0.599
Newly formed bone	Normal bone	0	0	0	0
	Implanted bone	0	44 ± 3.87	47.8 ± 3.56	54.8 ± 1.92
	p-value	-	0.005*	0.005*	0.005*

28 and 42, and between Ti and Ga-Si-Ti on days 28, 42, and 56. No statistically significant differences were found between Ti-Ga and Ga-Si-Ti, indicating comparable mineralization trends at those time points.

In the digital subtraction analysis, linear bone density in the PA view was evaluated on days 14 and 28. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test (table 6) showed statistically significant differences in newly formed bone within each group ($p < 0.05$), with Ga-Si-Ti demonstrating

the highest mean values. Kruskal-Wallis analysis (table S6) also confirmed significant intergroup differences in new bone formation at these early stages, supporting the utility of subtraction radiography in detecting early osseointegration.

Evaluation using paralleling radiography

Paralleling intraoral radiography was employed to assess bone density changes in cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone around

Table 4: Intergroup comparison of newly formed bone density among Ti, Ti-Ga, and Ga-Si-Ti implant groups across all time intervals (Kruskal-Wallis test)

Group	14 th Day	28 th Day	42 nd Day	56 th Day
Ti	-	17 ± 2.2	27.8 ± 4.7	43.2 ± 1.9
Ti- Ga	-	44.4 ± 2.6	54.6 ± 9.6	50.8 ± 7.4
Ga-Si-Ti	-	44 ± 3.8	47.8 ± 3.5	54.8 ± 1.9
p-value	-	0.009*	0.006*	0.021*

Table 5: Pairwise comparison of newly formed bone density between groups (Ti vs. Ti-Ga, Ti vs. Ga-Si-Ti, and Ti-Ga vs. Ga-Si-Ti) on Days 28, 42, and 56 (Mann-Whitney U test)

Group	Compared with	28 th Day	42 nd Day	56 th Day
Ti	Ti-Ga	0.009*	0.009*	0.094
	Ga-Si-Ti	0.009*	0.009*	0.009*
Ti-Ga	Ga-Si-Ti	0.750	0.142	0.209

Table 6: Intragroup comparison of new bone density between Day 14 and Day 28 using digital subtraction radiography (Wilcoxon signed-rank test)

Group	14 th Day (mean)	28 th Day (mean)	p-value
Ti	17.00	27.80	0.043*
Ti-Ga	42.40	49.80	0.043*
Ga-Si-Ti	44.40	56.60	0.043*

the implant site. Corresponding images for the Ti, Ti-Ga, and Ga-Si-Ti groups are shown in figure 4a, b and c. Grayscale values were quantitatively analyzed using the Soredex Digora software system.

The summary of grayscale variations for cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone on all time points is provided in supplementary tables S1 to S5. Statistical analysis using the Kruskal-Wallis test demonstrated that there were no significant differences in cortical bone density among the three groups on any of the four time points ($p > 0.05$), although the Ga-Si-Ti group showed the highest average grayscale values, followed by Ti and Ti-Ga (table S7). Similarly, no statistically significant differences were observed in trabecular bone density across the groups (table S8), though Ga-Si-Ti consistently recorded higher mean values. For newly formed bone, no significant intergroup differences were detected on days 14, 28, 42, or 56 ($p > 0.05$); however, grayscale analysis revealed the highest average bone density in the Ga-Si-Ti group, followed by Ti and Ti-Ga (table S9).

Overall, both PA and paralleling radiographic methods confirmed that the Ga-Si-Ti implant group exhibited earlier and more robust new bone formation compared to the other groups, particularly evident in the digital subtraction and grayscale analysis. These findings underscore the potential of Ga-Si-Ti alloys for enhanced osseointegration and support the effectiveness of quantitative 2D digital radiography as a non-invasive tool in preclinical implant evaluation.

Discussion

Radiographic images were used to qualitatively assess implant placement within the implant bed. A decrease in grayscale indicated bone mineral loss, while an increase suggested gain. Traditional radiography detects bone mineral density (BMD) changes exceeding 12%, whereas digital radiography can detect subtle changes as low as 1–5% [11]. Previous studies, such as [12], qualitatively evaluated implant positioning and bone changes using digital radiographs. However, this study extends that work by introducing quantitative evaluation using 2D digital radiography, enabling precise BMD assessment through density-calculation software.

In the Posterior-Anterior (PA) whole-body view, BMD of medial/lateral cortical, trabecular, and newly formed bone was assessed on days 14, 28, 42, and 56 in Ti, Ti-Ga, and Ga-Si-Ti groups. The Ga-Si-Ti group consistently showed the highest BMD, particularly in trabecular and newly formed bone. Significant differences were noted between Ti and Ti-Ga, and Ti and Ga-Si-Ti groups, especially on days 28–56. In contrast, Ti-Ga and Ga-Si-Ti groups showed similar trends beyond day 28, indicating comparable osseointegration during later stages. No significant BMD changes were seen in the cortical bone between implanted and adjacent non-implanted sites, likely due to consistent animal handling and nutrition.

Trabecular bone density decreased in the Ti group up to day 42

likely due to inflammation but improved by day 56, indicating healing. Ti-Ga and Ga-Si-Ti groups showed increased opacity by day 28, attributed to Ga and Si elements promoting early osseointegration [13]. These results align with [14]. New bone formation appeared after day 14. In the Ti group, BMD increased significantly from day 28, reaching levels similar to adjacent cortical bone by day 56. In Ti-Ga and Ga-Si-Ti groups, similar mineralization was achieved by days 42 and 28, respectively, consistent with in vitro findings on Si-induced osteogenesis [15].

Digital subtraction radiography, used in this study, enabled early detection of bone formation by minimizing anatomical noise and enhancing contrast. This technique revealed meaningful changes in newly formed and trabecular bone as early as day 14, affirming its sensitivity [16]. The Ga-Si-Ti group showed the most consistent and significant increases in BMD, with osseointegration complete by day 28, compared to day 46 in the Ti-Ga group. These results support findings by [17]. Paralleling radiography was used to analyze grayscale-based density profiles. While no statistically significant BMD differences were noted across groups ($p > 0.05$), grayscale values suggested higher new bone formation in the Ga-Si-Ti group, followed by Ti and Ti-Ga. Limitations included 2D imaging of 3D structures and motion artifacts in small animals. However, radiographic trends and mean grayscale values supported increased mineralization and osteocyte formation [18,19]. By day 28, Ga-Si-Ti implants showed more new bone formation than Ti-Ga. Remodeling was evident by day 56, confirmed by both digital radiographs and polyfluorochrome studies. These findings align with [20].

Conclusion

This in vivo study demonstrates that digital 2D radiography including PA view and paralleling radiographs can be effectively used for quantitative assessment of osseointegration. While prior studies used PA imaging qualitatively, this study provides a novel quantitative approach, showing measurable increases in BMD and bone formation across groups. Among tested implants, Ga-Si-Ti alloys exhibited the highest BMD and most rapid osseointegration. These results underscore the potential of Ga-Si-Ti for clinical applications. Digital radiography proves to be a sensitive, non-invasive method for evaluating biomaterials and monitoring bone regeneration over time.

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